

Women in AI – Challenges and Solutions

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Abstract—Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become one of the most transformative technologies in this century and permeates nearly every facet of our existence. Despite its rapid growth and deep societal impact, the field of AI faces a significant gender disparity. Women are underrepresented in AI, both in industry and academia. This gender gap is not just a social issue -- it has a profound impact on the development of AI systems, potentially leading to biased applications that can exacerbate existing inequalities. The status of women in AI reflects broader systemic issues in STEM fields, including gender biases in education systems, the lack of role models, and a work culture that often marginalizes women’s contributions. This paper explores the challenges faced by women in AI and presents approaches that the Women in High Performance (WHPC) Chapter at University of Florida took to overcome the barriers.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence, gender bias

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become one of the most transformative technologies in this century impacting nearly every facet of our existence. Despite its rapid growth and deep societal impact, the field of AI faces a significant gender disparity. Women are underrepresented in AI, both in industry and academia. According to the Global Gender Gap Report of 2023 [1], women make up only 30 percent of the AI workforce globally, roughly four percentage points higher than in 2016. This gender gap is not just a social issue -- it has a profound impact on the development of AI systems, potentially leading to biased applications that can exacerbate existing inequalities due to the lack of female workforce in AI and data science fields. The status of women in AI reflects broader systemic issues in STEM fields, including gender biases in education systems, a lack of role models, and a work culture that often marginalizes women’s contributions. This paper explores the challenges faced by women in AI and presents approaches that the Women in High Performance (WHPC) Chapter at University of Florida took (UF) to overcome the barriers

II. CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN IN AI

The underrepresentation of women in AI is rooted in several factors, including systemic biases, a lack of visibility, and cultural environment in the field and society. The gap in AI is particularly pronounced due to the field’s heavy reliance on computer science, mathematics, and engineering – fields in which women have been underrepresented historically. Furthermore, for women working in the AI and data science fields, retention remains a serious challenge due to implicit bias, gender stereotyping and lack of mentorship and role models.

A. Challenges in education

The pipeline for women entering AI begins to narrow at the educational level, where fewer women pursue degrees in computer science, math, engineering, and related fields than their male counterparts. This disparity is often attributed to a lack of early exposure to computing concepts, gender stereotypes that discourage girls from pursuing technical subjects, and the absence of female role models in these disciplines.

B. Challenges in the workplace

The challenges to women’s participation in AI are multifaceted across every stage in career development including hiring, promotion, and achieving recognition. Furthermore, the lack of female role models in leadership positions represents fewer examples of successful career paths, discourages women from entering the field, and creates a cycle of underrepresentation. The Insight Report [1] shows that for high-level leadership roles such as VP and C-suite, women only represent 17.8% and 12.4%, respectively. Additionally, women in AI often have to navigate a work culture that may be unwelcoming with instances of sexism and microaggressions further contributing to a hostile work environment.

C. Bias in AI Systems

A large amount of research has studied the gender biases in AI systems and models [2][3]. One of the root causes is the lack of diversity in AI development teams, which allow AI systems and models to perpetuate gender stereotypes and discrimination. When women are underrepresented in the development team, the perspectives and experiences of half the population are inadequately reflected, which results in AI applications that are biased against women and that reinforce existing gender stereotypes. Thus, building a diverse AI workforce is crucial for developing AI systems that are free from bias.

III. APPROACHES TO IMPROVE WOMEN’S PARTICIPATION IN AI

Addressing these challenges and improving women’s participation in AI requires a holistic approach that tackles educational, institutional, and cultural barriers. In the spring of 2020, UF began a campus-wide AI initiative making AI the centerpiece of a major long-term effort to become a national leader in AI research, education, and workforce development. In the same year, UF Information Technology (IT) Research Computing (RC) team founded the UF WHPC Chapter. To encourage and promote women’s participation in AI, the Chapter adopted several strategies to actively engage faculty and student organizations in AI research, education and mentorship.

A. Education initiatives

The underrepresentation of women in AI begins at the educational level. To encourage the participation of female and under-represented student groups, we focused on the following activities:

1. **Campus AI training:** in alignment with UF's AI initiative, the RC team organized hundreds of AI trainings and workshops covering a variety of AI topics at different levels of proficiency. We specifically engaged student organizations for female and other underrepresented groups on campus to encourage their participation in these AI education sessions.
2. **Community outreach:** in collaboration with faculty members, we co-hosted an AI Summer camp in 2024 for local high school students from minority school districts and recruited an equal number of female and male students for the program, which provided incredible opportunities for young students to learn AI basics, meet with UF AI faculty, and learn about how AI is applied in various research disciplines. The hands-on experience with AI tools and technologies helped spark students' interest and build confidence in acquiring knowledge and skills in AI and data science.

B. Research opportunities

To help demystify the AI field and promote the participation of female students in AI research, we partnered with faculty and student organizations to help them embark on their AI journey by providing research opportunities and computing resources.

1. The UF WHPC team partnered with faculty members who are committed to addressing gender inequality issues and matched them with female undergraduates to work on AI research projects, funded by NSF undergraduate research scholarships.
2. We also partnered with student AI organizations to provide them with free computing resource allocations on UF's high performance computing system. Our state-of-the-art computing resources helped these students gain hands-on experience with AI projects and sharpen their AI skills.

C. Mentorship and networking

Mentorship plays a vital role in supporting women in AI.

1. **Networking:** since the establishment of the UF WHPC chapter, we have routinely hosted WHPC events, such as panel discussions and workshops. We invited highly accomplished female AI faculty to share their experiences and guidance for navigating challenges and career development. The workshops are faculty-led discussions focusing on inherent gender biases and ethics issues in AI systems. These events have been great channels for female students to connect with experienced female faculty in AI and find mentors. They are also effective platforms for students to share their own challenges in their studies and campus life and find support from their peers.
2. **Employment opportunities:** RC has been providing on-campus part-time jobs and internships for students to work in the department to gain work experience in high performance computing. The RC AI team also hired female students to work on AI consulting projects with research groups across research disciplines. These part-time jobs provide students with first-hand work experience and professional development and make them more competitive in the job market.

IV. CONCLUSION

The challenges women face in AI are multifaceted, requiring a concerted effort by the AI community to improve equality and close the gap in education and employment. By taking approaches that focus on AI education, mentorship, and networking, we can enhance the participation of women in AI and ensure that women have an equal opportunity to contribute to and lead in the field of AI. Only then can we ensure that current and future AI technologies are developed in a way that is unbiased and beneficial to all of society.

- [1] Insight Report, Global Gender Gap Report, June 2023, https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2023.pdf.
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